

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Unnecessary macros\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to the use of *macros* in situations where functions or *structs* would be more appropriate. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[inline macro\]](#): When code is implemented as a *macro* but could be implemented as a conventional function in Elixir, we can use this refactoring to remove this smell, improving the readability of the code.
1. [\[Extract function\]](#): When creating a *macro* is unavoidable, but part of it could be implemented as a conventional named function, we can extract this part of the macro's code and encapsulate it into a conventional function, which the *macro* will then call. This approach improves code organization and readability while leveraging the macro for its specific role.
 2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): After extracting the function, it may eventually be necessary to move it to another module to make the code more cohesive.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Complex else clauses in with\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when *with* statements handle all of their error clauses in a single *else* block. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): When an *else* clause in a *with* statement is used to handle different types of errors that may occur during the execution of the *with* clauses, the code can become confusing. To address this issue, we can use this refactoring to transform expressions in the *with* clauses into separate private functions. Each of these private functions will handle a specific error type, decentralizing the error-handling task.
2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): After extracting the new functions responsible for decentralizing error handling, the *with* statement will no longer need an *else* clause. Therefore, we can use this refactoring to remove the *else* clause.

 - [\[Remove redundant last clause in "with"\]](#): Optionally, if the last clause of the *with* statement used to chain operations is redundant, we can use this refactoring to make the code less verbose and more readable.
 - [\[Moving "with" clauses without pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, if the *with* statement does not perform pattern matching in the first and/or last clauses, we can use this refactoring to make the code more idiomatic and readable.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Divergent change\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a single module is frequently modified in multiple places for unrelated reasons. Modules that group together many functions that do not share a common purpose are prone to Divergent Change. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Splitting a large module\]](#): This smell can be removed by creating new cohesive modules and moving related functions into them.
2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.

 - [\[Moving a definition\]](#): If there is already a module *B* that is more suitable to accommodate a function that makes module *A* less cohesive, we can simply move this function from module *A* to module *B* to remove this smell.
 - [\[Behaviour extraction\]](#): This smell can be removed by creating a new cohesive module *B* and moving related functions of module *A* into it. Thereby, we can use this refactoring to transform module *A* into a *behaviour definition* and create module *B* as a *behaviour implementation* of module *A*, thus achieving this goal.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Code organization by process\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to code that is unnecessarily organized by processes. A process itself does not represent a code smell, but it should only be used to model runtime properties (e.g., concurrency, access to shared resources, event scheduling). When a process is used for code organization, it can create bottlenecks in the system. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Remove processes\]](#): When code unnecessarily uses a process for organizational purposes where a simple module with functions would suffice, this refactoring can be used to remove the unnecessary concurrent processes and replace them with regular Elixir modules.
2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): When we transform a process into a regular Elixir module, some functions that previously implemented process callbacks (e.g., *GenServer*) may become unnecessary and can therefore be removed using this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Modules with identical names\]](#) smell? *

This code smell is related to possible module name conflicts that can occur when a library is implemented. Due to a limitation of the Erlang VM (BEAM), also used by Elixir, only one instance of a module can be loaded at a time. If there are name conflicts between more than one module, they will be considered the same by BEAM and only one of them will be loaded. This can cause unwanted code behavior. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): In Elixir, there is a naming convention for modules that should be followed when implementing libraries. According to this convention, a library should use its own name as a prefix (namespace) for all its module names (e.g., `LibraryName.ModuleName`). When a library does not adhere to this naming convention, it can lead to name conflicts for the library's clients. To remove this smell, we can rename the modules of a library to adapt them to this convention. It is important to be careful when performing this refactoring on already released libraries, as it may cause breaking changes in client code.
 - [\[Move file\]](#): If the same directory contains two modules with the same name defined in different files, we can use this refactoring to relocate one of these modules to a new directory. Naturally, we will also need to rename the moved module to conform to the naming convention for modules in Elixir, which recommends using the directory name as a prefix (namespace) for all module names contained within it (e.g., `LibraryName.ModuleName`).
1. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): As explained in the previous refactoring, when a library does not follow the naming convention for modules, it can lead to name conflicts in their clients. To remove this smell in already released libraries, we can use this present refactoring on the modules of a library, adapting the names of the copies to this convention. Meanwhile, the modules with names outside the convention should be marked as deprecated but not immediately removed, to avoid breaking client code.
 2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): When modules deprecated by the previous refactoring have remained deprecated long enough for clients to adapt to the new naming conventions, we can use this refactoring to permanently eliminate them, thereby removing the risk of name conflicts.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Large class\]](#) smell? *

Although Elixir does not support classes, functions can be grouped by *modules* in a similar way. When a module is not cohesive, it deals with multiple distinct business rules, tending to have many functions and lines of code, becoming large. This makes maintenance difficult. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Splitting a large module\]](#): When a module does the work of two or more, it becomes large, poorly cohesive, and difficult to maintain. In these cases, we should split this module into several new ones, moving to each new module only the attributes and functions with purposes related to their respective goals.
 2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity to also apply this refactoring.
- [\[Behaviour extraction\]](#): This operation is helpful if it's necessary to have a list of operations and behaviors that client modules can reuse, thus reducing their sizes.
 - [\[Moving a definition\]](#): When a function is defined in module *A* but is more suited to the responsibilities of module *B*, we can move it to *B* to reduce the size of *A*.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Long function\]](#) *
smell?

Poorly cohesive function, made up of too many lines of code that group together many different responsibilities that could be separated into smaller functions with a single responsibility each. Generally, any function longer than ten lines should make you start asking questions. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Extract function\]](#): If a comment is needed to explain some part of the function body, this refactoring can be used to create a new function to be called at the location of this comment, thus decreasing the size of the original function.
 - [\[Transform nested "if" statements into a "cond"\]](#): If a function uses many nested *if* conditionals, this can greatly increase its size. In these cases, we can use this refactoring to decrease the size of the function.
 - [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): If a function performs operations that can be delegated to other existing functions, it may become unnecessarily long. In these cases, we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the original function.
 - [\[Remove dead code\]](#): If a function contains code that is no longer used, it may become unnecessarily long. In these cases we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the original function.
 - [\[Simplifying checks by using truthness condition\]](#): When we know that a given data item can be *nil* and we need to return a default value if it is indeed *nil*, we can use this refactoring to reduce the number of lines in a function while maintaining clean and self-explanatory code.
 - [\[Generalise a function definition\]](#): When different functions have equivalent expression structures, these equivalent expressions can be generalized into a new higher-order function, thus reducing the size of the original functions.
 - [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): When a function has many branches in its body that depend on values received as parameters, it can become unnecessarily long. We can use this refactoring to create short multi-clauses for the original function, where each clause handles a different branch.
 - [\[Replace pipeline with a function\]](#): When a function is unnecessarily long due to a pipeline of function calls that can be replaced by a single call, we can use this refactoring to address the issue.
 - [\[Default value for an absent key in a Map\]](#): A function can have its number of lines reduced by using this refactoring to replace the use of *if* statements that check the return of *Map.has_key?/2* with a call to the *Map.get/3* function.
 - [\[Defining a subset of a Map\]](#): When a function is unnecessarily long because it manually creates a subset of a *Map* by individually accessing each of the desired key/value pairs, we can use this refactoring to delegate this task to a call to *Map.take/2*.
 - [\[Pipeline using "with"\]](#): When a function uses nested conditionals solely to control a sequence of function calls, it can become long. By using this refactoring, we can make the function more idiomatic and reduce its number of lines of code.
 - [\[Remove redundant last clause in "with"\]](#): This refactoring can reduce the number of lines of code used by a *with* statement and consequently shorten the size of the function that uses this statement.
 - [\[Modifying keys in a Map\]](#): When a function is unnecessarily long because it manually replaces a *Map* key with a new key using *Map.get/2*, *Map.put/2*, and *Map.delete/2* functions together, we can use this refactoring to delegate this task to a call to *Map.new/2*, thus significantly reducing the volume of lines of code.
 - [\[Remove nested conditional statements in function calls\]](#): When a function uses unnecessary nested conditional statements, it can become long and less readable. In such circumstances, we can use this refactoring to replace the unnecessary nested conditional statements with less bulky code that maintains the same behavior, thus making the code simpler and more readable.
 - [\[Splitting a definition\]](#): When the refactoring [Merging multiple definitions] is used carelessly, there is a risk of creating a long function. In such cases, we can undo this operation using the present refactoring, thereby generating smaller, separate functions.
 - [\[Merging match expressions into a list pattern\]](#): If a function uses many lines of code with expressions that assign results to temporary variables but can be replaced by a single *list* generated through pattern matching, we can use this refactoring to reduce the size of the function.
1. [\[Convert nested conditionals to pipeline\]](#): When a function uses nested conditionals solely to control a sequence of function calls, it can become long. By using this refactoring, we can give the function a more functional appearance and reduce the number of lines of code.
 2. [\[Replace function call with raw value in a pipeline start\]](#): When using the previous refactoring to remove this smell, we may also encounter an opportunity to apply the present operation, making the refactored code more idiomatic.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

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* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

[Voltar](#)

[Enviar](#)

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